

DIGITAL LEADERSHIP IN EDUCATION: A PROGRESSIVE ROADMAP FOR PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL PRINCIPALS IN THE DIVISION OF PANGASINAN I

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 4

Pages: 394-412

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1766

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11177179

Manuscript Accepted: 04-04-2024

Digital Leadership in Education: A Progressive Roadmap for Public Secondary School Principals in the Division of Pangasinan I

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Abstract

The study assessed the level of digital competency leadership of the school principals in SDO Pangasinan I based on their perceptions and their teachers. The study determined their profile variables, level of digital competency, and the challenges encountered in their workplace. The study also determined the significant difference between the responses of the school principals and their teachers' responses in their level of digital leadership competency and the level of digital leadership competency of the respondents across profile variables. It also determined the significant relationship between the level of digital leadership competency of the school principals and the challenges they encountered in their workplace. Findings revealed that the majority of the respondents were 41 to 50 years old and 51 to 60 years old, which was categorized as an adult and near retirement stage. Also, school principals perceived that they had a high level of digital competency among Equity and citizenship advocates, Visionary planners, Empowering Leaders, Systems Designers, and Connected learners, whereas teachers' perceptions were rated as high. In addition, there is a significant difference across the group regarding Empowering Leaders. Also, the variables on highest educational attainment and length of service significantly affect the overall level of digital leadership competency of the school principals. Further, there is a significant negative association between the level of digital leadership competency of school principals and the challenges they encounter in their workplace. However, indicators that rated the high level of challenges the school principals encountered included technological, individual, domestic, and community indicators. Thus, a strategic technology plan was proposed to address the principals' challenges and improve the level of digital competency leadership in their workplace.

Keywords: *digital leadership, equity and citizenship advocate, empowering leader, system designer connected learner*

Introduction

The education system worldwide is embracing and infusing the tenets and ideals of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which mostly prompted the call for the advancement of the digital economy, robotics and scientific advancement, and automation technology. Nevertheless, specific human-related abilities remain relevant, making them essential values of the human capital sought by the upcoming industrial era (Thannimalai & Raman, 2018).

Interestingly, all learners in the present era need different skills to survive in highly competitive workplaces, develop into engaged citizens, and achieve global standards to become part of the global community. UNESCO (2014) asserted that quality education and training equip people with skills, knowledge, and attitudes to obtain decent work and prepare for a new world. Consequently, through the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2030, UNESCO demarcated the teachers' role in ensuring quality education and learning, anchored on ensuring equitable, quality education and lifelong learning for all by 2030 (Morales et al., 2016).

The school, as the institution that provides learning and produces a productive leader of the country, is at the height of facing the challenge of how it will fully infuse and embrace the advancement of technology. Thus, the challenge requires all administrators and teachers to adapt with an open mind to changes and advances brought by technology's rapid growth and development.

Balc (2001), as cited by Banoglu (2017), emphasizes that it is important to consider technology management broadly, not just in terms of technology supply but also in terms of a more comprehensive viewpoint of the entire management process. Considering technology as both the physical and mental facilities via which a company changes its inputs to outputs. Traditionally, educational institutions use technology for pedagogical and instructional purposes. While utilizing educational tools effectively in these tasks, it is crucial that the school's principal keep abreast with the current trends in school administration to align with them and thereby improve the school personnel's technical knowledge and abilities.

The impact of technology leadership roles in schools is broad. This is affirmed by Flanagan & Jacobsen (2003), as cited by Banoglu (2017), the responsibility for anything from ensuring classroom lighting is appropriate to the promise of safe computer use. Using technology to further democratic ideas is another example of ensuring that everyone has access to technology and avoiding gender inequality in the use of technology.

Ergo, it is underscored by Sukanya Chamchoi (2018), that the organizational environment is quickly evolving in the 21st century. The technological environment is both a contributory factor and a hindrance factor in management. Digital leadership of the school heads must be capable of taking the organization forward through technological or digital innovation, and competent in driving educational institutions through systematic management, resulting in more efficient work.

The International Association of Educational Technology (ISTE) and the Professional Education Association have set international standards for information technology development for administrators in education (National Educational Technology Standard for Administrators: NETS-A) formulated into five areas: (1) vision leadership (2) Digital learning culture (3) Professional practice excellence (4) Systematic improvement and (5) Digital citizenship. Each area has defined tasks for information and communication technology leadership (International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE), 2009). In this digital era, educational administrators are an essential component. Hence, it is reiterated by Chaokasem Suphawat et al. (2019) that school administrators must develop themselves to have knowledge, abilities, characteristics, skills, and experience in educational administration to develop educational institutions to be modern and suitable for changes in the digital era with innovative thinking skills, technology, and innovative leadership.

Consequently, administrators and teachers should prepare to adopt, infuse, and use technology in the school setting and equip themselves with the latest trends in technology skills. Administrators must act as technology leaders and teachers as facilitators to provide the skills and knowledge for 21st-century education (Roblyer & Doering, 2014).

An administrator's responsibility is to bring his teachers to adopt and infuse technology into the learning process as well as to improve their skills and proficiency in using technology in teaching to attain the demands of the digital economy and workforce. Since technology is rampant and one of the fastest growing in today's age, the need for administrators to adapt and apply technology developments is indispensable. Administrators are advised to develop their digital leadership to meet the new world order (Hacıfazlıoğlu et al., 2011).

For this reason, the new roles of administrators could be listed as seeking new technologies, establishing computer labs, preparing teachers to integrate ICT effectively across the curriculum, and infusing their leadership capabilities in technology integration. Seemingly, technology leaders in the school, who are the administrators, must be familiar with educational technology goals and standards. They must understand the benefits of technology being integrated into education and be able to develop staff development programs for teachers (Beytekin, 2014).

Unfortunately, Apsorn, Sisan, and Tungkunan (2019) explained the problems in educational technology, most of which are administrators' lack of readiness to use information technology. Administrators still lack the readiness to learn technology and do not see the importance of innovation and information technology. Likewise, administrators lack knowledge, experience, and expertise in using media to create innovative media and information technology and various elements for teaching and learning. Further, most of the school heads still lack qualities in ICT leadership, which is a major problem affecting educational administration and management at the school level and overall education.

As concrete evidence, there were 262 school administrators showed the results of the remote meeting questionnaire of the school administrators via the Google Meet application several times and the feedback after the meeting found that school administrators still lack knowledge and skills in VDO conferences and the ability to use online meetings in various formats at a very good level 11.83 %, good level 19.08 %, moderate level at 22.14% and the level should be improved obtained 49.95%, which when taking the results from the moderate level and the level should be improved equals 72.09 percent. As a result, this should accelerate the development of educational institution administrators in using digital technology urgently to keep up with technology in the present time (Office of Chaiyaphum Primary Education Area 2, Thailand, 2020, Sheninger (2014) pointed out that there are still school leaders who are reluctant and misunderstand the use of digital technologies, such as the role of social media and the advantages of using digital devices. Some principals do not master ICT and digital technology competencies. In the same manner, Leong, Chua, and Sathiamoorthy (2016) found that there is a correlation between the knowledge of technology integration and principals' ability to motivate themselves to implement whole school changes.

Similarly, key findings from the CoSN's 2019 K-12 IT Leadership Survey Report (2019) showed that one of the top three challenges faced by technology leaders, which remained the same from 2017 to 2019, was insufficient professional development. Technology leaders reported lack of relevant training and the unavailability of professional training. School leaders have the responsibility to encourage and support teachers to integrate technology in learning and to teach, especially when the Internet of Things is rapidly making its way into classrooms in ways never imagined. With Smart whiteboards and alternative interactive digital media being widely utilized during interactive classroom learning, school leaders must keep abreast with the new technologies.

Thus, school leadership preparatory training should include technology to produce future-ready school principals who can lead teachers and students as learning experiences become virtual and ubiquitous (Aldowah et al., 2017; Esplin, 2017). Moreover, school technology leaders aim to propel learning and teaching forward toward student achievement. Thus, technology leaders must take advantage of technology to transform, impact learning, and create a shared vision for how technology can meet the needs of all learners (National Education Technology Plan Update, 2017).

School leaders must envisage and facilitate the use of technology in this ubiquitous digital world to students who are now digital natives. However, according to a report by the World Economic Forum (2019), poor leadership could be the biggest barrier to a successful Fourth Industrial Revolution strategy.

Moreover, a study conducted by Unal et al. (2015) revealed no significant difference in the technology leadership self-efficacy levels

in terms of the school level. Seemingly, not only the administrators but also teachers had a problem when it came to technology infusion. A study by Apau (2017) found that teachers lack knowledge of technology content. For him to recommend that teachers and lecturers should continue to model the use of technology in teaching to update them on the technological and pedagogical content further.

In many schools, technical difficulties become a major problem and a source of frustration for students and teachers and cause interruptions in the teaching and learning process. Lack of technical assistance and no repair on it, enables teachers not to use the computer for temporarily (Jamieson-Proctor et al., 2015). Teachers will be discouraged from using computers because they fear equipment failure since they are not given any assistance on the issue. In Türel and Johnson's study (2012), it was revealed that technical problems become a major barrier for teachers. These problems include low connectivity, virus attack, and printer not functioning (Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015).

However, teachers' lack of personal experience with technology presents a challenge. To incorporate technology-based activities and projects into their curriculum, teachers must first find the time to learn to use the tools and understand the terminology necessary for participation in those projects or activities (Starr, 2011). If these technologies are utilized properly, they can be a tool for teachers and students to help them gain experiences using new technologies.

Schindler (2017) provided the barriers that hinder the effective implementation of technology into classroom teaching and learning, such as factors like access, time, resources, training, attitudinal effects, beliefs, practices, institutional and administrative support, experience, and resistance are as well restraining forces to technology integration.

Meanwhile, technology can also distract students in the classroom from their learning activities. Technical tools like laptops and mobile phones can distract students from their learning activity and disrupt classroom activity if not used properly. Mobile phones distract students because of the problems of ringing during classroom discussions, use in cheating during classroom assessments, multi-tasking by students, and the use of cameras in the classroom, which could lead to privacy issues.

Moreover, laptops and computers can be used for instant messaging, using Facebook, watching movies or videos irrelevant to classroom topics, and distracting other students. Technological resources such as computers, laptops, and mobile phones used in teaching and learning activities have both constructive and destructive effects on the academic environment affecting the students (Carbonilla & Bhati, 2016).

In the Philippine education context, school leaders, who are the administrators and teachers, are now transforming themselves on what the Industrial Revolution 4.0 is pushing with to elevate the current education system in which their digital leadership is pointed-out on how it will further enhance the technical proficiency of their teachers.

Further, teachers, as a vital part of nation-building, sustain an organizational culture that focuses on continual improvement of educational programs, teachers' capacities and skills, and student learning. The practice of learning should be a desirable style of personnel awareness that they value organizational goals and strategies to achieve improved learning outcomes.

The integration of technology by leaders and teachers was affected by inadequate training, ICT incompetency, and limited ICT access. Evidently, there is a gap in technology integration among teachers and school leaders who are not skilled in managing technology integration at schools; for example, many teachers in Malaysia faced challenges implementing Learning Management Systems like the Frog Virtual Learning Environment (Cheok & Wong, 2016).

In the context of the Philippines, Sagcal (2018) underscored that there is an existing "technology gap" in the Philippines. A technology gap is defined as the gap between new technology and a country that has yet to acquire that technology. Countries across the globe, therefore, vary in their acquisition of that technology, resulting in what experts call a "digital divide" resulting in a highly competitive market and industry towards globalization. The Philippines is a developing country, but the technology has kept up with most of the world. Computer technology is being introduced to secondary schools, but DepEd has recently introduced ICT to students as early as Grade 4. Hence, DepEd plans to conduct massive training to improve the ICT skills of elementary teachers. One major challenge in boosting ICT in schools is the logistics and the size of DepEd (Philippine News Agency, 2018).

On the other hand, DepEd recognizes the key role of information and communications technology (ICT) in improving education. The Internet, with its capacity to hold infinite resources, will provide accessible and comprehensive education for students in the country. Teachers can also benefit from learning tools that do not require traditional logistics and multiple materials in their teaching. DepEd has launched the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS), a portal for online teaching and learning materials created by teachers and education partners. This will help our learners have more access to relevant, up-to-date and quality education materials. It also provides a database for our educators to derive their lessons. These materials will assist them in their lesson plans and may provide contextualized classroom discussions (Garcia, 2016).

Today, many schools nationwide continue to struggle with limited budgets for acquiring enough desktop computers and laptops. According to a broadband policy brief released by Arangkada Philippines last year, almost eighty percent (80%) of public schools in the Philippines still do not have Internet access. Too many young Filipinos are unable to take full advantage of advancements in digital technology when compared with other countries because a significant portion of the public school system does not have Internet access.

Likewise, access to primary education is a fundamental human right, and by integrating ICT into our public education system, we are giving our youth the capability to compete globally in today's digital environment (Garcia, 2016).

Similarly, the Philippine Education Technology Master Plan was introduced, which has the following operational targets (Bonifacio, 2015: 5): (1) all public secondary schools shall be provided with an appropriate educational technology package; (2) 75% of public secondary schools shall have a computer laboratory room equipped with basic multimedia equipment; (3) all public secondary schools shall have an electronic library system; (4) 75% of public secondary schools teachers shall have been trained in basic computer skills and the use of the Internet and computer-aided instruction; and (5) all learning areas of the curriculum shall be able to integrate the application of ICT, where appropriate (Tomaro & Mutiarin, 2018).

The Philippine public schools lack computers, are also not connected to the internet, and are not used effectively. The unstable power supply in the area and the fluctuating supply of electricity is detrimental to the present scarce computer facilities. Thus, computers can only be used for minimal work. For today's learners, 21st-century skill development has become a need to be successful in the future. For teachers, these skills have become the focal point of best practices in instruction and education. Although the emphasis on 21st-century skills for K- 12 learners has been around since the 1980s and 1990s, they have taken education worldwide by storm with the emergence of new technologies and innovative tools for the classroom. Focusing on communication, critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity, 21st-century skills are increasingly being emphasized in classrooms around the globe. Yet, the 21st-century skills movement centers on developing lifelong learners who are prepared for life and work after graduation. Learners today need to prepare for becoming members of a global society in which technology and media are valuable resources (McGuire (2018).

The rapid changes in the world require learners to be flexible, take the initiative as well as lead when necessary, and to produce something new and useful. To be educated in today's world requires mastering core subjects, 21st-century themes, and 21st-century skills. To help learners attain proficiency in 21st-century skills, teachers and administrators need education support systems that strengthen their instructional, leadership, and management capacity.

Thus, 21st-century skills are indeed one of the most discussed concepts in today's education settings. New standards for learners are replacing the basic skill competencies and knowledge expectations of the past. To meet this global challenge, schools must be transformed to enable learners to acquire the creative thinking, flexible problem-solving, collaboration, and innovative skills they will need to succeed in work and life (Sural, 2017).

Furthermore, all learners in the present era need different skills to survive in highly competitive workplaces, develop into an engaged citizen, and achieve global standards to become part of the global community.

The Department of Education (DepEd) envisions the rise of public schools of the future, which are anchored on the pillars of education, namely quality, access, equity, resiliency, and well-being, and governance as enabling mechanisms. One of the most important factors in attaining this vision is the infusion of technology in the educational landscape. However, international, national, and local assessments reveal that the current situation is bleak, and there is still lots of work to be done if one aim to be at par with the rest of the world.

An assessment conducted by the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) through the Organization for Economic Cooperation Development (OECD), which tested the students' knowledge in Reading, Mathematics, and Science, reflected the alarming performance of our Filipino test-takers. The Philippines fared significantly lower achievement than all the ASEAN countries participating in PISA 2018. Filipino learners aged 15 years old, attained a general mean score of 350 points in Reading Literacy, Mathematical Literacy, and Scientific Literacy in the Philippines, which is lower than the OECD average score of 489 points. The results triggered the Department of Education to find interventions for Filipino learners to be academically aligned with the global world.

The low proficiency level results from the PISA 2018 contributes to the reports presented by the DepEd Regional Office I through the Curriculum and Learning Management Division(2021) discussed that based on the analysis of the other assessments like the National Achievement Test (NAT), survey results and validation conducted with the Education Program Supervisors (EPSs) in English, Mathematics, and Science, and the Chiefs of the Curriculum and Implementation Division (CID) and Schools Governance Division (SGOD) in DepEd Region I, the perceived gaps that may have contributed to the low results of the PISA 2018 were: (a) low mastery of subject matter; (b) inappropriate use of teaching strategies; (c) no constructive alignment of content, instruction, and assessment; (d) poor test construction; (e) no quality-assured Learning Resources (LRs); (f) no quality-assured assessment; (g) absence on the provision of Technical Assistance (TA); and (g) no common Monitoring and Evaluation (M & E) Tool.

Moreover, as per observation by the two Division Testing Coordinators of the region from the PISA Field Testing Trials conducted simultaneously last March 11, 2020, at San Nicolas National High School, Ilocos Norte, and San Quintin High School Foundation, Inc., Pangasinan II, most of the sampled test takers were not familiar with the use of the computer-based assessment. In addition, most of the learners were not feeling easy on the mouse's use in moving the computer's cursor. Most of them were first-timers and some got nervous while answering the test items. The two Division Testing Coordinators suggested that teachers should be trained in making Computer- Based Assessments for their Quarterly Examinations so that all learners shall eventually become knowledgeable to manipulate computers, particularly on the use of the mouse (click and drag) for the computer-Based Assessment.

Based on the monitoring report of the Schools Division Offices of the region on the status of the technology capability of schools, the following were bottlenecks encountered by the schools as limited computer laboratory equipment; insufficient computer laboratory room, intermittent internet connection due to the location of the schools; downgraded hardware and software for the Senior High School track offering animation. Also, teachers need ICT / digital skills to adapt to learning needs and situations. The need for digitization of ICT processes and systems such as records management is evident in schools and offices.

Undeniably, technology has emerged as a powerful tool revolutionizing various aspects of our lives, and education is no exception. Technology provides students with easy-to-access information, accelerated learning, and fun opportunities to practice what they learn. It enables students to explore new subjects and deepen their understanding of difficult concepts (School of Education Online Programs, 2023).

Indeed, time and technology also created new breed of learners, teachers, and administrators with unique skills and competencies. The entire school community in general requires a new educational set-up that is more innovative, data-based, and research-oriented, productive, and relevant.

The application of technology has the power to transform educational experiences, bridge geographical divides, and expand access to quality education. By embracing technology, Philippine schools can provide engaging learning experiences, foster connectivity, and collaboration, and personalize education to meet the needs of individual students. However, it is essential to address challenges such as connectivity, infrastructure, and equitable access to technology to ensure that the benefits of technology are realized by all. With continued investment, support, and innovation, technology can pave the way for a more inclusive and equitable education system, transcending the limitations of physical distance and unlocking the potential.

On this note, Van Niekerk and Van Wyk (2014) argue that the principal is the leader who must initiate and sustain the integrated use of technology in education by modeling and incorporating technology in management and administrative operations and practices. As cited by Karahan, Canbazoglu Bilici, and Ünal (2015) discovered that the need for school administrators to adapt to technological developments is crucial, as technological developments are evolving.

Technological developments experienced in this information age affect educational systems and accordingly the teaching and learning process. As a result of changes occurring in the field of technology, school directors' managerial support for the acquisition of educational technologies by schools, updating the existing technologies, the recruitment of specialized personnel, the use of new tools and equipment by teachers and the training of teachers.

Therefore, schools need to be managed in a technology-friendly manner and should have a good technological infrastructure. In order to establish such a good infrastructure, school directors need to lead their schools in this direction. As a new type of leadership for school directors, technology leadership is defined by Tanzer (2014) as "the person who takes the initiative in the effective and efficient use of technology in the organization, influences, directs and manages the organization in this direction". Technology leadership in education is an integrated process involving the motivation of the associates at school for learning, utilization, and integration of technology into the environments they are working (Hacıfazlıoğlu et al., 2016a; Hayytov, 2017).

Indeed, infusing technology into the educational system can be a powerful way to fill educational gaps and improve learning outcomes. Analyzing the strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities (SWOT) in priority improvement areas (PIAs) of the current educational landscape can be an effective way to craft and develop and implement programs and projects (PAPs). Supported by an effective monitoring and evaluation (M & E) system, and continuous improvement (CI), PAPs based on reliable gap analysis can yield a significant improvement in the basic education system.

In the Philippine education context, school leaders, who are the principals/administrators and teachers, are now transforming themselves on what the Industrial Revolution 4.0 is pushing with to elevate the current education system in which their technological leadership is pointed-out on how it will further enhance the technological proficiency of their teachers for the improvement of learning outcomes.

Digital leadership allows school principals to be the administrator, to initiate programs, motivate teachers, and inspire students to be fully equipped with information technology concepts and applications. This benefits the school and become globally competent.

Therefore, this research study intended to determine the level of digital leadership competency of public secondary school principals in the School Division of Pangasinan I. This provided educators across all governance levels condensed information that can aid the formulation of new policies, planning and implementation of intervention programs and activities to a shared responsibility and accountability.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess, analyze, and evaluate the level of digital leadership competency of public secondary school principals in the School Division of Pangasinan I for the SY 2023-2024. Further, this helped the school organizations develop management and leadership capability in digital technologies to lead to digital development and as a competitive advantage in its internal and external operations. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents along :
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 number of years as school principal; and
 - 1.5 number of trainings related to technology- driven instruction?
2. What is the level of digital leadership competency of the public secondary school principals as perceived by the respondents themselves and their teachers along the following standards:
 - 2.1 equity and citizenship advocate;
 - 2.2 visionary planner;
 - 2.3 empowering leader;
 - 2.4 systems designer; and
 - 2.5 connected learner?
3. Is there a significant difference between:
 - 3.1 responses of the school principals and their teachers' responses in their level of digital leadership competency; and
 - 3.2 level of digital leadership competency of the respondents across profile variables?
4. What are the current challenges encountered by the schools principals in terms of:
 - 4.1 technological barriers;
 - 4.2 individual barriers;
 - 4.3 domestic barriers;
 - 4.4 institutional barriers; and
 - 4.5 community barriers?
5. Is there a significant relationship on the level of digital leadership competency of the school principals along with the challenges they encountered in their workplace?
6. What plan can be proposed to address the findings of the study?

Literature Review

On Profile of the Respondents

Age refers to the length of an existence extending from the beginning to any given time. Gender, on the other hand, refers to the behavioral, cultural, or psychological traits typically associated with one sex (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2020).

Educational attainment is the highest ISCED level of education an individual has successfully completed. This is usually measured with respect to the highest educational programme successfully completed which is typically certified by a recognized qualification (ISCED, 2011). The study of Cabahug (2016) findings were as follows: (1) The age of the public elementary school principals are almost evenly distributed, most of them are females, married, earned or graduated their Ed.D/Ph.D degree, either NQEP or NQESH passers, and have attended division to international level trainings. (2) The principals themselves are "excellent" along all areas of the 21st century managerial competencies on teachers' performance, pupils performance, physical facilities development and on curriculum implementation is very high. (3) Principals' 21st century managerial competencies significantly vary as to their highest educational attainment and number of years as principal.

Problems arose in each category of managerial competencies which are pressing, thus, the need for an immediate resolution. Thus, there is a need for a strategic enhancement plan to address the problems encountered by the principals to enhance their 21st century management approaches.

On Level of Digital Leadership Competency of the Respondents

Digital leadership of educational directors is of great importance in terms of the execution of the education system planned within the school, the effective and efficient use of technology during education, instructional and evaluation activities, the encouragement of the personnel working for the integration of technology into system and the provision of continuity in this encouragement (Can, 2008). Therefore, school directors as technology leaders have to take responsibility for the effective use of information and communication technologies in school management and in the class, acquire the required competencies to do so and improve their competencies. There are some roles to be undertaken by school directors as technology leaders. These roles are summarized in the literature to be related to the following: Technology-orientation, instructional program, infrastructure, facilitation, planning, communication, personal development, supervision, ethics, safety, technology budget, public relations, change and technology policy.

As explained by Flanagan and Jacobsen (2013), technological leadership roles in schools touch many responsibilities ranging from ensuring the appropriateness of lighting facilities in classrooms to the assurance of healthy computer usage and also ranging from using technology in ways that support democratic principles and protecting the equal access to technology to preventing gender inequality in technology usage. All these educational technology leadership roles and responsibilities should be evaluated through scientifically

well-defined dimensions whereby educational research organizations and researchers developed standards and models on this field.

On the Challenges Encountered by the Respondents Along Digital Leadership

Morioka (2016) entitled, Promoting ICT education in developing countries: Case Study in the Philippine. The paper generally highlighted the ICT education settings through a depiction of the situation in two schools from the rural (100 kms from Manila) and suburbs (50 kms from Manila). It was first and foremost emphasized that despite the wide adoption of ICT in developed countries, in the Philippines, a developing country, there is a gap of accessibility present between rural and urban areas of the country.

This said gap was grounded by Kubota, Yamamoto and Morioka (2018) in the educational setting by delving into the ICT-adoption statuses of schools in the country. The need for ICT integration to the educational set-up of the schools are given emphasis as it is part of the goal of the government of the Philippines that ‘a people-centered inclusive and development-oriented information society, where everyone can create, access, utilize and share information and knowledge’, is established (Kubota et al., 2018: 3). Also, the new millennium ushered in an information revolution that puts pressure to the countries to catch up to the latest technological developments.

One of the key policy actions of the government, under the Department of Education was the introduction of the subject, Technology and Home Economics (THE), a subject combining the Home Economic and Livelihood Education (HELE) in the secondary level (Magno, 2006; Kubota, Yamamoto, and Morioka, 2018).

Furthermore, Kubota, Yamamoto, and Morioka (2018) also highlighted the key policies of the Philippine Department of Education that emboldens the integration of ICT in the curriculum of education. These are as stated: Technology must be studied as a separate subject, and then applied to other learning areas as a tool for learning how to learn. Teaching-learning must not be textbook-driven but should include the application of ICT, whenever appropriate. An education modernization program will equip schools with facilities, equipment, materials and skills, and introduce new learning and delivery system, capitalizing on recent technological developments.

On Significant Difference and Relationships of the Variables Involved in Digital Leadership Competency

Domeny (2017) showed that there is no significant relationship between principals' digital leadership and the implementation of digital learning by teachers – the relationship between the two variables is weak. However, others have still found a strong relationship between the two dimensions (International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE), 2021). The overall ISTE Standards for Administrators demonstrate that ISTE-A offers strong standards to guide and direct principals in their role as digital leaders.

The study of Hamzah (2021) et.al. identified the level of digital leadership displayed by principals, the level of teachers' digital teaching practices and the elements of principals' digital leadership that predict the level of teachers' digital teaching. About 400 secondary school teachers in Hulu Langat District, Selangor were involved in this study. A multiple regression found that only digital citizenship is a strong predictor of teachers' digital teaching. It is also revealed that that the ability to plan and organize digital leadership programs is important and can help improve students' academic performance, despite the pandemic.

Cruz, Villena, Navarro, Belecina, and Garvida (2016) conducted their studies to determine the level of managerial performance of school heads, their strengths and weaknesses in the different areas of school management as perceived by school heads themselves, their teachers, and senior students. Findings of the study revealed that school heads exhibited very satisfactory level in performing their managerial functions in all management areas identified. It also revealed that there were significant differences in the managerial performance of school heads in the areas of vision, mission and goals toward financial and budgeting, physical plant and facilities, community relations and management of school improvement plan. The derived data on the weaknesses of school heads in performing managerial functions in identified areas of school management provided the basis in proposing an enhancement plan that may be used in improving their functions and in providing a key to more development programs for school heads in the division as recommended in this study.

On Digital Leadership Enhancement Program

Studies on challenges faced by school technology leaders in Australia recommended that further research on professional development needs for leaders should be carried out. In the United States, limited studies have been carried out on technology leadership and its effect on technology integration among teachers (McLeod & Richardson, 2011). Furthermore, Davies (2016), Kowch (2009), and O'Dwyer et al. (2014) recommended that further research on guidelines and development programs for technology leadership should be carried out.

Previous research on technology leadership only used the National Education Technology Standards-Administrator (NETS-A) to study technology integration (Alkrdem, 2014). Not many studies have analyzed the relationship between the five constructs of technology leadership. As well as the importance and performance of these constructs with technology integration in secondary. In addition, studies conducted by Evers et al. (2016) suggested that professional development for technology leaders should be studied.

In the studies conducted by Luechaet et al. (2022), it was found that the digital leadership of school administrators consists of 7 components and 22 indicators. There was a low level of desirable Conditions for Digital Leadership of School Administrators. Also, the Desirable Conditions for Digital Leadership of School Administrators obtained the highest level. The necessity of developing digital leadership among school administrators obtained the highest value was digital vision leadership.

Methodology

Research Design

This research study utilized the descriptive-survey method of research. A descriptive survey uses surveys to gather data about varying subjects. This data aims to know the extent to which different conditions can be obtained among these subjects.

Calmorin (2007) pointed out that descriptive researches are purposive processes of gathering, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions, practices, beliefs, process, trends, and cause-effect relationships about such data with or without the aid of statistical tools. Calmorin (2007) further claimed that survey signifies the gathering of data regarding present conditions through the use of questionnaire. Descriptive studies describe phenomena associated with a subject population or to samples of that population that have certain common characteristics (Cooper et al., 2009).

Participants

This study included one hundred forty-three school principals of Pangasinan Division I. They are based on the data obtained in SDO - SGOD Pangasinan I report. The distribution of respondents is presented in Table 1. In addition, to validate the claims of the respondents, there was a total of 70 teachers represented in every district to counter validate the responses of the respondents.

Instruments

Letter of request was submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent through the school heads for the permit to conduct the study and administer the questionnaire. After the approval of the request, each respondent was provided with the questionnaire. The researcher explained to the respondents the purpose of the study.

The study employed a survey questionnaire to collect data needed to achieve the objectives of the study. The researcher utilized sets of questionnaires in gathering data from the teacher respondents. The questionnaire was composed of the following parts:

Part I focused on the profile of the respondents.

Part 2 included items on the level of digital competency standards which included equity and citizenship advocate, visionary planner, empowering leader, systems designer, and connected learner based from the ISTE(International Society for Technology in Education, 2018) as cited by Johnson (2021) as perceived by themselves and their teachers.

Part 3 clarified the level of challenges encountered in integration digital leadership in schools in terms of technological barriers, individual barriers, domestic barriers, institutional barriers, and community barriers. The item questionnaires on this part were modified by the researcher which was based from the studies conducted by Rayray (2022) and Baticulon et. al., (2021).

Further, the research instrument was subjected to content validation using the five-point scale questionnaire. Evaluator's comments and suggestions were incorporated and served as bases in the modification of the instrument.

The validity of the data-gathering instrument was described in terms of the following scale values with the corresponding descriptive equivalence:

<i>Scale Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalence</i>
4.21-5.00	Highly Valid
3.41-4.20	Valid
2.61-3.40	Moderately Valid
1.81-2.60	Fairly Valid
1.00-1.80	Not Valid

Further, the average ratings of the evaluators were computed to determine the content validity with corresponding transmuted ratings to ensure the usefulness and validity of the information to be gathered. In this study, it was found out that the questionnaire is highly valid with a value of 4.94 which implies that the instrument was described as highly valid that covered all the areas needed in the study.

In addition, the questionnaire was subjected to the reliability test in which the questionnaire will be administered to a sample of 30 respondents in the municipality. In addition, the questionnaire was subjected to the reliability test in which the questionnaire was administered to a sample of 30 respondents in the districts. Such tests were used to measure the consistency of the test administered.

Procedure

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools in the analysis of the data to be gathered.

Sub-problem 1. The profile of the respondents was described through frequency counts and percentages.

Sub-problem 2 and 4. The level of digital competency and the level challenges encountered by the respondents in the workplace were analyzed using weighted mean and were interpreted based on the scale below:

Mean Scale Range	Description
4.21 -5.00	Very High
3.4 - 4.20	High
2.61 -3.40	Moderate
1.81 -2.60	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Very Low

Weighted Mean is an average computed by giving different weights to some of the individual values. If all the weights are equal, then the weighted mean is the same as the arithmetic mean. It represents the average of a given data. The Weighted mean is similar to arithmetic mean or sample mean. The Weighted mean is calculated when data is given in a different way compared to an arithmetic mean or sample mean.

Sub-problem 3.a. The difference between the level of digital competency as perceived by the respondents themselves and their teachers, t-test for independent samples were employed.

Sub-problem 3.b. The difference on the level of digital competency across profile variables, One-Way Analysis of Variance were determined. The One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether there are any statistically significant differences between the means of three or more independent (unrelated) groups.

Sub-problem 5. The relationship between the level of digital leadership competency of the school heads along with the level of challenges they encountered in their workplace were determined via Pearson product moment of correlation. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient is a measure of the strength of the linear relationship between two variables. It is referred to as Pearson's correlation or simply as the correlation coefficient. If the relationship between the variables is not linear, then the correlation coefficient does not adequately represent the strength of the relationship between the variables.

Sub-problem 6. A progressive roadmap / strategic plan was proposed via a training matrix. The list of relevant program , projects and activities as well as strategies were crafted by the researcher address the priority areas of the school principals on digital technology leadership.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Public Secondary School Principals in the School Division of Pangasinan I

The profile of the respondents which included the personal and professional- related variables which included their age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service as school head and the number of relevant trainings attended for 3 years, respectively.

Table 1 presents the data on the frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the public school principals in Schools Division of Pangasinan I.

Table 1. *Profile of the Public Secondary School Principals in the School Division of Pangasinan I n=143*

Profile	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	31 to 40 years old	20	14.0
	41 to 50 years old	51	35.7
	51 to 60 years old	51	35.7
	61 years old and above	21	14.7
Sex	Male	80	55.9
	Female	63	44.1
Highest Educational Attainment	Masters with units only	10	7.0
	Master’s Degree	21	14.7
	Doctorate with units only	50	35.0
	Doctorate Degree	62	43.4
Length of service as a school principal	5 years and below (young in service)	40	28.0
	6-10 years (moderately young)	41	28.7
	11-15 years (old in service)	11	7.7
No. of relevant trainings attended for 3 years	16 years and above (very old in service)	51	35.7
	1-5	40	28.0
	6-10	41	28.7
	Above 10	62	43.4

Age. It can be gleaned from the table that 51 or 35.7 % of the respondents were 41 to 50 years old and 51 to 60 years old, which is described as adult and near retirement stage, respectively. Also, 20 or 14.0 % of the respondents were moderately young with age bracket of 31-40 years old whereas 21 or 14.7 % belong to age bracket of 61-65 years old were retirement stage . Data implies that most of the school principals were adults and near retirement stage. This study is unparallel to the studies of Ovilo (2022) and Gagar (2020) when most of the school heads respondents belonged to the age bracket of 41-50 who were adult.

Sex. The table shows that 80 or 55.9% were males while 63 or 44.1 % of the respondents were females. This data implies that the school principals of SDO Pangasinan I was largely dominated by males. This data is unparallel to the study conducted Borres (2021) on her study that most of the respondents were females.

Highest Educational Attainment. There are 62 or 43.4% of the respondents were with EdD/PhD degree holder while 50 or 35.0 % had Ed.D/Ph.D units. There are 21 or 14.7 % who earned MA/MS degree holder while 10 or 7.0 % of the respondents with masteral units. This finding implies that school principals are aware in their personal and professional development to become equipped as school leaders in their respective stations.

Number of Years in Service. Data shows that half of the respondents (51 or 35.7) served 16 years and above which described as very old in service. Also, 41 or 28.7 % obtained 6-10 years in service which described moderately young whereas 40 or 28.0 of the respondents had 5 years and below which were relatively young in service. Looking at the above figure , data denotes the majority of the school principals are very long in the service with well-experienced as to their knowledge, skills, and abilities to be a school principal.

Relevant In-Service Trainings Attended. Nearly half of the principals, with 62 or 43.4 % have attended above 10 relevant trainings held at various levels whereas less than half of the respondents percent less than 10 relevant trainings. The finding reveals that the school principals were capacitated on digital technology leadership to enhance their personal and professional growth. Further, it could be said that the rest enjoy the opportunity of attending seminars at one level or the other but not at all levels of training. It is imperative for public school principals that they attend training and seminars to keep them abreast with the trends in education, particularly in areas of school leadership and administration, and supervision. Attending training is also an opportunity for public school heads to widen their horizons as professionals as a result of their interaction with experts.

Level of Digital Leadership Competency of the Public Secondary School Principals as Perceived by the Respondents Themselves and Their Teachers

This portion determined the level of technological leadership competence of the respondents. It was done by requesting them to rate themselves as well as their teachers as regards their level of technological leadership competence along Equity and Citizenship Advocate, Visionary Planner, Empowering Leader, Systems Designer, and Connected Learner.

As shown in Table 2 below, it presents the level of technological leadership competence of public school principals along with the aforementioned variables.

Table 2. *Level of Digital Leadership Competency of the Public Secondary School Heads as Perceived by the Respondents Themselves and Their Teachers*

<i>A. Equity and Citizenship Advocate As a school principal, I...</i>	<i>School Head</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>
1. conduct professional development and support to address gaps in using technology to meet the learners needs	3.85	H	4.11	H
2. provide devices, bandwidth, and online resources available to all students at school, home or public areas through funding, partnerships and collaboration	3.78	H	3.87	H
3. support teachers to personalize and differentiate teaching, participate in real-time and asynchronous virtual collaboration in authentic and engaging learning opportunities through classroom response system (Nearpod, Quizlet, Kahoot, Socrative, Mentimeter, Padlet)	3.92	H	3.97	H
4. model the best practices on digital citizenship along responsible online behavior, including the safe, ethical, and legal use of digital technologies both online and offline.	3.99	H	4.03	H
5. use collaborative tools such as Zoom, Webex, Ms Teams, Facebook messenger, viber to engage in virtual social action and to increase online strategies.	4.20	H	4.03	H
Weighted mean	3.95	H	4.00	H
B. Visionary Planner As a school principal, I...				
1.engage education stakeholders in developing and adopting a shared vision for using technology to improve students access and learning practice.	4.27	VH	4.13	H
2. create a strategic plan (AIP/SIP) that articulates how technology will be used to enhance learning	4.35	VH	4.13	H
3. build data collection, benchmark, and regular review to provide evidence that efforts remain aligned with the plan and guide changes for doable strategies for using technology to transform learning.	4.14	H	4.04	H
4. communicate effectively with stakeholders to gather input on the plan by using online survey , collaborative digital work spaces, online feedback , QR code, etc.	4.07	H	3.95	H
5. share lessons learned, best practices, challenges and the impact of learning with technology with other education leaders who want to learn from this work.	4.42	VH	4.09	H
Weighted mean	4.25	VH	4.07	H

C. Empowering Leader				
1. empower teachers to exercise professional agency, build teacher leadership skills and pursue personalized professional learning.	4.50	VH	4.36	VH
2. build the confidence and competency of teachers to put the standards for students and teachers into practice.	4.50	VH	4.29	VH
3. inspire a culture of innovation and collaboration that allows the time and space to explore and experiment with digital tools.	4.36	VH	4.05	H
4. support teachers in using technology to advance learning that meets the diverse learning, cultural, and social-emotional needs of individual students.	4.57	VH	4.24	VH
5. develop learning assessments like e-portfolio, tools and applications that provide a personalized, actionable view of student progress in real time.	4.36	VH	3.89	H
Weighted mean	4.45	VH	4.17	H
D. Systems Designer As a school principal, I...				
1. lead teams to collaboratively establish robust infrastructure and systems with sufficient bandwidth, network, software and applications needed to implement the strategic plan.	3.93	H	3.73	H
2. ensure financial or human capital resources for supporting the effective use of technology for learning are sufficient and scalable to meet future demand.	4.14	H	3.95	H
3. protect information and data through precautionary planning and actions to ensure that students and staff observe effective privacy.	4.28	VH	4.12	H
4. craft contextualized policy / guidelines in maintaining vigilance in the face of innovations in cybercrime, cyberbullying in schools.	4.20	H	4.13	H
5. establish partnerships with the community stakeholders that support the strategic vision, achieve learning priorities and improve operations.	4.13	H	4.15	H
Weighted mean	4.14	H	4.02	H
E. Connected Learner As a school principal, I...				
1. set goals to remain current on emerging technologies for learning, innovations in pedagogy and advancements in the learning sciences.	4.36	VH	4.15	H
2. participate regularly in online professional learning networks to collaboratively learn with and mentor other professionals.	4.20	H	3.99	H
3. use technology to regularly engage in reflective practices that support personal and professional growth.	4.28	VH	4.04	H
4. develop the skills needed to lead and navigate change and advance systems in school / workplace.	4.28	VH	4.04	H
5. promote a mindset of continuous improvement such as openness to feedback and willingness to learn for how technology can improve learning.	4.29	VH	4.29	VH
Weighted mean	4.28	VH	4.10	H
Overall Weighted mean	4.21	VH	4.07	H

Note: 1.00-1.80 Very Low (VL); 1.86-2.60 Low (L); 2.61-3.40; Moderately High (MH); 3.41-4.20 High (H); 4.21-5.00 Very High (VH)

Along with Equity and Citizenship Advocate. Based on the data on Table 4, the majority of the school principal and teachers' respondents are rated high along equity and citizenship advocate with an overall weighted mean of 4.14 and 4.02, respectively. Along these indicators that are rated high includes the conduct professional development and support to address technology gaps/ concerns; provide devices, bandwidth, and online resources available to all students via partnership/linkages; support teachers to personalize and differentiate teaching through real-time and asynchronous virtual collaboration; model the best practices on digital citizenship along responsible and ethical online/ offline on the use of digital technologies; and use collaborative online tools to increase online strategies. Data implies that the school principals have high competence as perceived by themselves and their teachers which denotes that technology leaders are trying to harness the high-interest medium to engage students in the classroom, since learners are digital natives.

Moreover, technology leaders must support the integration of technology and make it a top priority as stressed by Cox & McLeod, 2014 cited by Johnson (2021). The literature also supported the advantage of teachers taking students' preferences into consideration when implementing digital technology in the teaching process. If digital based instruction was infused into instructional practices, teachers may have guided students in using social media effectively and also in creating effective strategies against negative effects of online interactions (Tezci & Icen, 2017). This means that students must have equal access to these learning opportunities.

Additionally, based on this study there are some indicators on equity and digital citizenship advocate that the school principals may looked into and gave careful and rational decisions like technology inequality that may have restricted students especially in some schools near coastal and mountainous areas and building principals to support their teachers in engaging in innovative practices using digital media. Similarly, the secondary principals' practices have to be very evident in schools that may positively increase equity, inclusion, and digital citizenship practices for both staff and students with the use of digital media technologies within the school setting.

Findings of this study are unparallel to the study conducted by Johnson (2021) revealed ten themes based on technology leadership

experiences not typically evident in mainstream educational leadership texts. Recommendations were derived from this study provided in : (1) making leadership decisions within their districts as well as providing enabling support mechanism such as professional development agencies, principal preparation programs , and potential partners for linkages (2) creating innovative approaches to instructional and social media problems faced by administrators in 21st century schools through a stronger, more transparent connections among stakeholder groups; (3) utilizing the student-led social media teams in Nebraska as a powerful tool in the way students connect, learn, and communicate in a global society.

Along Visionary Planner. The relationship with stakeholders was not a specific solution to a problem, however, it is cited that “a shared vision for the school community embraces the notion that schools cannot operate effectively without an important partnership with the larger community” (Robbins & Alvy, 2004, p. 5 as cited by Johnson (2021).

Data indicate that school principals’ responses perceived that they are very highly competent with a weighted mean value of 4.25 whereas teachers’ perceived their level of competency of their school principals as high with a computed value of 4.07 in terms of visionary planner. The said statements are focus on the engagement of education stakeholders in developing and adopting a shared vision for using technology to improve students access and learning practice; creating a strategic plan (AIP/SIP) that articulates how technology used to enhanced learning ; building data collection, benchmark, and regular review to provide evidence that efforts remain aligned with the plan and guide changes for doable strategies; communicating effectively with stakeholders through online platforms; and sharing lessons learned, best practices, challenges and the impact of learning to stakeholders.

Data implies that the school principals had high competence as perceived by themselves and as perceived by their teachers, they are rated high. This means that these activities on visionary planning are to be manifested and practice evidently in school settings. As such, integrating technology in the development of their school plans aligned to the DepEd vision, mission, and goals inclusive with the participation of community stakeholders who are their partners in education are to be intensified in actual setting.

The literature supports the current study which is focused on visionary planner, Johnson (2021) indicated that social media was utilized to connect with multiple stakeholder groups. Ergo, a technology leader must be willing to share with other educational leaders (ISTE, 2018). Many principals were utilizing social media as a productive means of driving culture and communicating with a variety of stakeholders from parents to community members (Sheninger, 2014). Principals could interact with larger audiences using social media than they could with newsletters or telephones (Ferriter & Ramsden,2011).

In the same vein, Dougherty et al. (2013), said that effective leadership and governance with the integration of technology are necessary to promote a more cohesive and collaborative culture and ethos in schools and to establish good cooperation with the wider community. School leaders have a key role to play. Their good leadership, governance, and support from stakeholders are vital.

Along Empowering Leader. It is showed in the table that the perceptions of the school principal in terms of empowering leader is very high while on teachers’ responses rated as high with the mean values of 4.45 and 4.17, respectively. Such indicators include are the following : (1) empowering teachers to establish teacher leadership skills and personalized learning ; (2)building the confidence and competency of teachers relating to standards and practice ; (3) inspiring teachers through establishing a culture of innovation and collaboration through maximizing digital tools; (4)supporting teachers in using technology to advance learning that meets the diverse learning needs ; and (5) developing digital learning assessments that can be used online and offline. It implies that school principals as they practice empowering leaders to their staff is not congruent to the perceived responses of teachers. Based on their self-assessment, they are very high in empowering their staff, however it is rated high by the teacher respondents. This attributed the fact that the perceived knowledge and competence of the school principals linked to habits and practice to create a culture of positivity and empowerment.

This is in consonance in the literatures cited that leaders inspire a culture of teamwork (ISTE, 2018). Participatory decision- making increased participants' commitment and developed a shared sense of direction (Bolman & Deal, 2017 as cited by Johnson (2021). It has been shown to be an empowering tool to increase both morale and productivity (Levine et al., 2001). Bolman and Deal (2017) stressed, “Effective leaders help group members communicate, work together, and do what they are there to do” (p. 177). Hackman (2002) emphasized that leadership is responsible for building teams and giving team members direction that is challenging, energizes team members and generates strong collective motivation to perform well.

Along with Systems Designer. It is reflected in the table that both responses of the school principals and teachers’ respondents are rated high with the mean values of 4.14 and 4.02, respectively. Item statements that are rated high includes : (1)leading the teams to collaboratively establish robust infrastructure and systems ; (2) ensuring financial or human capital resources for technology support ; (3) protecting information and data through precautionary planning and actions; (4) crafting contextualized policy / guidelines in maintaining vigilance in the face of innovations in cybercrime, cyberbullying in schools; (5) establishing partnerships with the community stakeholders that support the strategic vision to improve operations. Data implies that there is still a need to enhance the technological leadership competency of school principals in terms of system design. Also, the need to provide sufficient bandwidth, network, software and applications needed to implement the strategic plan along with schools’ programs, projects and activities to support DepEd thrust and initiatives.

This finding is unparallel to the study conducted by Miller (2022) found out that most school leaders in the had limited understanding

of how the standards of digital competency could provide a holistic and comprehensive guide to transform learning. It is noted that the perception of technology as necessary but separate from a critical tool in the learning process, due to the fact that school leaders described technology implementation as having a device for every student.

Ergo, systemic leaders build and lead teams to implement, sustain, and continually improve the infrastructure needed to meet the goals of the strategic plans and future demands (ISTE, 2018). Thus, systems depends on human nature and organizational needs. It is stressed by Bolman & Deal (2017) that organizations need people - their energy, effort, and talent), and people need organization (for various intrinsic and extrinsic rewards they offer to the school.

Ahmed (2016) added that School management plays a significant part in the advancement and existence school; therefore, it becomes imperative to enlighten the school management regarding social media’s implementation and its significance. It is noted that principals were a key factor in the implementation and integration of educational technology systems (Berrett et al., 2012 as cited by Johnson (2021).

Along Connected Learner. Data reflects that the overall mean values of 4.28 and 4.10, respectively is described as very high on school principals’ responses while the teachers’ responses rated as high as they assessed their principals’ digital leadership competency in terms of connecting the learners. Among these statements are setting goals to be updated on technological breakthroughs; participating regularly in online professional learning networks; using technology to regularly engage in reflective practices that support personal and professional growth; developing the skills needed to lead and navigate change and advance systems in school / workplace and promoting a mindset of continuous improvement to improve learning. Data implies that school principals put into practice the different strategies to connect with learners.

In the study of Cox and McLeod (2014) examined twelve qualitative interviews with school principals and outlined the importance of administrators’ use of social media to create transparency and instill confidence: two principals noted that their schools had been impacted positively due to the social media use by the principals.

Based on the ISTE (2018), leaders remain up-to-date with new technology, and advancements in pedagogy . Some principals used social media professionally in terms of administrative processes, social needs, searching for information and entertainment for educational processes. School leaders who employ a strong social media communication plan earn the trust of their school communities, enjoy more positive feedback from stakeholders and benefit from a lively exchange of ideas with their off-site and extended community” (Powers & Green, 2016) as cited by Johnson (2021).

In general, the overall weighted mean values obtained 4.21 which rated as very high by the school principals whereas teachers ‘responses on their assessment to their school principals rated as high with a value of 4.07. This data supports that incongruence led to the school leaders’ perception with the idea that the principal as a technology leader along equity and digital citizenship, visionary planner, empowering leader, system designing and connecting learner is not sufficiently practice in school settings as reflected to teachers ‘responses. The need to cultivate a culture of excellence where the technology leaders fulfill the roles and responsibilities in leading and managing the school operations. Indeed, the skills needed for productive technology leadership in supporting teachers and students- led digital technology applications, tools and strategies.

Difference Between Responses of the School Principals and their Teachers’ Responses in their level of Digital Leadership Competency

Data on table 3 shows the difference between responses of the school principals and their teachers’ responses in their level of digital leadership competency.

Table 3. *Difference between responses of the school heads and their teachers’ responses in their level of digital leadership competency*

Digital Leadership Competency	School Heads		Teachers		Multivariate Test		Univariate Test	
	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Wilks' lambda	Sig.	Fc	Sig.
Equity and citizenship advocate	3.95	0.07	4.00	0.09			0.190	0.663
Visionary planner	4.25	0.06	4.07	0.09			2.875	0.091
Empowering Leader	4.45	0.05	4.17	0.07	0.871*	0.000	10.556*	0.001
Systems Designer	4.14	0.06	4.02	0.09			1.311	0.254
Connected learner	4.28	0.06	4.10	0.08			3.374	0.068

*Significant at 1% level

Table 3 shows the result of the test of difference between responses of the school principals and their teachers’ responses in their level of digital leadership competency using Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) . Moreover, univariate analysis of variance was also employed to further determine the difference in the level of digital leadership competency between school principals and teachers.

The overall test of difference using Wilk’s Lambda statistics revealed that there is a significant difference in the level of digital leadership competency between school principals and teachers. The univariate further revealed a significant difference across the group

in terms of Empowering Leader. Hence, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Data implies that the level of competency on the technology leadership as perceived by the school principals and their teachers differs in terms of empowering leader. This also means that technology leaders' empowerment is a significant factor in the technology leadership competency of a school principal.

A study by the National Endowment for Science, Technology and the Arts (NESTA), the study found that innovative experiences and empowered learners, increased students' ability to identify problems and find solutions (Sebba et al., 2009 as cited by Johnson (2021). Another study conducted 30 interviews in order to understand the limitations as well as the best practices associated with digital social innovation (Stokes et al., 2017). The study noted that using technology for social purposes must be done under leadership that was responsible and ethical (Stokes et al., 2017).

One may conclude that to be an empowering technology leader, one must be able to plan for a future that includes an ongoing process of change and growth. This must include meeting the diverse needs of individuals and learners as well as encompassing all stakeholders as part of the learning process.

As cited by Bolman and Deal (2017), effective leaders help group members communicate, work together, and do what they are there to do. Also, Hackman (2002) reiterated that leadership is responsible for building teams and giving team members direction that is challenging, energizes team members and generates strong collective motivation to perform well.

Difference between level of digital leadership competency of the respondents across profile variables

Data on Table 4 shows the difference between the level of digital leadership competency of the respondents across profile variables.

Table 4. *Difference between level of digital leadership competency of the respondents across profile variables*

Factors	Digital Leadership Competenc	Univariate Test	
		Statistic	Sig.
Age	Equity and citizenship advocate	10.52*	0.000
	Visionary planner	5.20*	0.002
	Empowering Leader	0.92	0.432
	Systems Designer	4.10*	0.008
	Connected learner	2.00	0.119
	Overall	2.49	0.065
Sex	Equity and citizenship advocate	0.71	0.403
	Visionary planner	2.07	0.153
	Empowering Leader	10.39*	0.002
	Systems Designer	0.56	0.455
	Connected learner	1.05	0.308
	Overall	1.05	0.308
Highest Educational Attainment	Equity and citizenship advocate	48.61*	0.000
	Visionary planner	48.10*	0.000
	Empowering Leader	4.75*	0.003
	Systems Designer	62.45*	0.000
	Connected learner	36.21*	0.000
	Overall	43.96*	0.000
Length of service as a school principal	Equity and citizenship advocate	29.20*	0.000
	Visionary planner	68.46*	0.000
	Empowering Leader	22.62*	0.000
	Systems Designer	23.03*	0.000
	Connected learner	94.50*	0.000
	Overall	86.06*	0.000
No. of relevant trainings attended for 3 years	Equity and citizenship advocate	5.27*	0.007
	Visionary planner	2.03	0.137
	Empowering Leader	3.48*	0.034
	Systems Designer	4.34*	0.016
	Connected learner	1.42	0.248
	Overall	3.26	0.04

*Significant at 1% level

Table 4 shows the result of the difference between level of digital leadership competency of the respondents across profile variables using robust test of equality of means (Brown-Forsythe test). A robust test was employed since the homogeneity of variance was not satisfied by the data.

Results revealed that the identified profile variables have a significant effect on the digital leadership competency of the school principals. Based on the result, the highest educational attainment and length of service as a school principal have a significant effect at 0.05 level of alpha on their overall level of digital leadership competency.

The findings of this study support the study conducted by Rayray (2021) found out that there is a significant difference in the level of technological leadership competence of public school heads along profile variables such as sex, civil status and relevant trainings in the regional, national and international levels.

Additionally, in the study of Turan (2022) results revealed that the teachers participating in the study consider their school principals' levels of technology-related leadership behavior as sufficient. There was no statistically significant difference observed between the technology leadership behaviors, and the variables of the school heads' gender, educational background, and professional seniority. Also, statistical significance was found between the teachers' perceptions regarding the school principals' technology leadership levels and the variables along length of work in the same school. The teachers with shorter length of work in the same school regard the technology leadership levels of school principals higher than those with longer length of work. The results obtained from the qualitative dimension of the research show that the school principals behave fairly in terms of enabling the use of technology, create the technology infrastructure, inform the teachers against cybercrimes and contribute to the increase of their motivation.

Challenges Encountered by the Schools Principals

The table depicts the current challenges encountered by the school principals along technological, individual, domestic, institutional and community concerns .

Table 5. Challenges Encountered by the School Principals n=143

<i>Challenges Technological</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>DE</i>
1. Lack of devices or limited access due to gadget sharing	4.02	H
2. Unreliable, slow, or no internet access	4.16	H
3. Lack of technical skills	3.52	H
4. Issues with the online learning platform	4.00	H
Weighted Mean	3.92	H
Individual		
1. Difficulty adjusting learning styles	4.08	H
2. Mental health difficulties	3.59	H
3. Physical health issues	3.10	MH
4. Practical concerns	3.44	H
Weighted Mean	3.55	H
Domestic		
1. Limited space conducive for studying	3.51	H
2. Need to fulfill responsibilities at home	3.79	H
3. Conflicts within the family	3.09	MH
4. Financial distress within the household	3.44	H
5. Need to work for extra income	3.58	H
6. Lack of basic needs	3.44	H
Weighted Mean	3.48	H
Institutional		
1. Administrative issues and lack of organization	2.81	MH
2. Poor communication between learners and educators	2.59	L
3. Inadequate skills of educators	2.80	MH
4. Poor quality of learning materials	3.01	MH
5. Gaps in knowledge and skills from current teaching methods	2.94	MH
6. Excessive cognitive load	3.15	MH
7. Limited opportunities to interact with peers	3.01	MH
8. Policies and practices that neglect student welfare	3.08	MH
Weighted Mean	2.93	MH
Community		
1. Limited support / collaboration/ partnership	3.58	H
2. Power interruptions	3.23	MH
3. Sociopolitical concerns	3.43	H
Weighted Mean	3.41	H
Overall Weighted Mean	3.38	MH

Data on Table 5 shows the overall weighted mean value of 3.38 which is described as moderately high that implies that the challenges / concerns are moderately serious problems. However, there are indicators that rated high level of challenges encountered which includes indicators on technological (3.92) , individual (3.55), domestic (3.48) and community (3.41). Item statement under technological concerns include unreliable, slow, or no internet access (4.16), Lack of devices or limited access (4.02), Issues with the online learning platform (4.00) , and Lack of technical skills(3.52).

Along with individual concerns, it is rated as high which described as much serious. Item statements include Difficulty adjusting

learning styles(4.08), Mental health difficulties (3.59), and practical concerns (3.44) whereas in terms of Domestic , item statements that are rated high involves the following : Need to fulfill responsibilities at home (3.79), Need to work for extra income (3.58), Limited space conducive for studying (3.51) , Financial distress within the household (3.44), and Lack of basic needs (3.44) . Similarly, along with the community concerns, item statements that are rated high or serious problem are indicators on Limited support / collaboration/ partnership (3.58) and sociopolitical concerns (3.43). Data implies that there varied challenges encountered by the school principal along with their level of technology competency leadership in terms of technological, individual, domestic and community. This means that varying indicators on the challenges encountered by the school principals along with their level of technology competency leadership.

This supports the study conducted by Sincar (2020) investigated elementary schools in Southeastern Turkey findings show that in assuming their roles as technology leaders school principals face various challenges, including bureaucracy, lack of resources, resistance to innovation, lack of in-service training, and poverty. Based on the findings, various measures are recommended to diminish bureaucratic obstacles and organize sustainable in-service training activities in order to overcome the challenges that school principals are facing in the context of technology leadership. Likewise, the study of Johari (2023) et.al found in their studies that the issues in school leaders' digital leadership are lack of knowledge, inability to use data for school planning, lack of computers and devices for teaching and learning activities, and lack of engagement. The implication of this study is to make education stakeholders, such as school leaders, aware of the importance of digital leadership in school.

Also, in the study of Raman et.al (2021) showed that the factors that prevented leaders and teachers from integrating information and communication technologies (ICT) in schools are lack of ICT training, teacher ICT competency, and access to ICT resources. This shows that there is a gap in technology integration in schools. Thus, school management should give priority to digital age learning culture and digital citizenship constructs to accelerate teachers' technology integration in schools.

Moreover Asio & Bayucca (2020) in their studies revealed that the administrators have varied results on the aspect of digital competence based on the statistical analysis. In terms of school readiness on distance learning, the schools were not yet ready to implement a distance learning scheme. For the perceived challenges, internet connection/ connectivity is the primary concern. Other challenges involve preparation, competencies, funding, and devices for distance learning. Based on the result of the study, the researchers provided some essential recommendations for the administrators, teachers, and other stakeholders.

Relationship on the Level of Digital Leadership Competency of the School Principals Along with the Current Challenges they Encountered in their Workplace.

Data on Table 6 shows the relationship on the Level of Digital Leadership Competency along Equity and citizenship advocate, Visionary planner, Empowering Leader, Systems Designer, and Connected learner of the School Principals Along with the Current Challenges they Encountered in terms of Technological, Individual , Domestic, Institutional, and Community barriers in their workplace.

Table 6. *Relationship on the Level of Digital Leadership Competency of the School Principals Along with the Current Conditions / Barriers they Encountered in their Workplace*

Digital Leadership Competency	Current Conditions / Barriers they Encountered in their Workplace									
	Technological barriers		Individual barriers		Domestic barriers		Institutional barriers		Community barriers	
	R	Sig.	r	Sig.	R	Sig.	r	Sig.	r	Sig.
Equity and citizenship advocate	-.197*	0.018	-.290**	0.000	-.487**	0.000	-.269**	0.001	-.437**	0.000
Visionary planner	-0.159	0.057	-.226**	0.007	-.339**	0.000	-.324**	0.000	-.335**	0.000
Empowering Leader	-0.022	0.795	-.224**	0.007	-.260**	0.002	-.348**	0.000	-.298**	0.000
Systems Designer	-0.136	0.106	-0.100	0.235	-.241**	0.004	-.279**	0.001	-.271**	0.001
Connected learner	-.234**	0.005	-.218**	0.009	-.344**	0.000	-.442**	0.000	-.303**	0.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 6 presents the relationship on the level of digital leadership competency of the school principals along with the current conditions / barriers they encountered in their workplace using Pearson - r Correlation. These coefficients were inferentially tested to determine if the computed coefficients are significantly different from zero.

The result revealed that there is a significant negative association between the level of digital leadership competency of the school principals along with the challenges they encountered in their workplace. The findings suggest that lower level of digital leadership competency is associated with a greater challenge they encountered in their workplace. Data implies that when the school principals faced with many challenges they encountered, this tend to lower the level of digital competency leadership of the school principals. Thus, addressing the challenges in school operations may improve the level of digital competency leadership of school principals. As cited by Adhi (2023), a leader needs to make plans and decisions based on available information. As stated by Brett (2020), a leader needs to be ready to react quickly and provide tactical solutions to urgent situations, and at the same time must be strategic in school operations. Failure to perform either of these well limits the chances of success of school leadership.

This study suggests the study conducted by Zhang et.al (2022) found the significant connections of technology leaders' practices regarding advocating equity and citizenship, planning vision, empowering practices, designing systems, and connecting professional learning to Technology-Enhanced Teaching (TET) and Technology-Enhanced Learning (TE). Technology leadership thus significantly influenced the engagement of technology-enhanced teaching and learning. Findings of this study shed light on how various benefits occur in teaching and learning when leaders successfully practice technology leadership in higher education.

Meanwhile, the study conducted by Jackson (2019) revealed that there was a relationship between principals' technological training and crafting of strategic technology plan and their school's implementation of technology. It is recommended in the study that principals must model practices in which they expect their teachers and students to replicate. Technology leaders at all levels must understand all of the components within the educational system that are required to lead technology integration as an instructional strategy and assist in making technology a transparent tool in teaching and learning.

Discussion

This study focused on the level of digital competency of school principals in Pangasinan Division I. The study made use of descriptive survey design of research which included the 143 permanent public school principals that were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency and Percentage, Weighted Mean, Multivariate Analysis of Variance, and Pearson - r correlation were statistical tools used. The study determined the profile of the respondents along age; sex; highest educational attainment; number of years as school principal; and number trainings related to technology-driven instruction. Also, the level of digital leadership competency of the public secondary school principals as perceived by the respondents themselves and their teachers along the following standards: Equity and citizenship advocate; Visionary planner; Empowering Leader; Systems Designer; and Connected learner. Likewise, the significant differences between responses of the school principals and their teachers' responses in their level of digital leadership competency; and the level of digital leadership competency of the respondents across profile variables were considered. The current challenges encountered by the schools principals and the significant relationship on the level of digital leadership competency of the school principals along with the challenges they encountered in their workplace were considered. The output of the study was the progressive roadmap- a proposed strategic technology plan for school principals.

Conclusion

Based on the foregoing significant findings, the following conclusions were drawn: (1) The public secondary school principals widely vary in their profiles and at certain instances their variations are in extreme cases and are distinctively male dominated group of respondents. (2) The public secondary school principals in this study are performing impressively more than well enough in their technological leadership but modeling of practices is possible in their present level of technological leadership competence is a stepping stone towards the highest level when they expect their teacher and students to replicate the outstanding practices. (3) Empowering a leader is a significant factor that differs on the level of digital competency of the school principals. (4) The highest educational attainment achieved and length of service are indicators related / may affect to the overall level of digital leadership competency of the school principals. (5) Varied indicators along technological, individual, domestic, and community are the possible challenges that the school principals encountered in their workplace. (6) The digital leadership competency of the school principals is associated with the challenges they encountered in their workplace.

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